

Stress tolerance — drought

Effect of water deficit on plant water status, growth, and yield of rice

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Recent research has challenged the traditional concept of keeping ricefields flooded throughout the cropping season. We conducted a glasshouse experiment to investigate the limit to which rice plants can be water-stressed without incurring significant yield losses. Our aim was to find ways to lessen the amount of water needed for irrigating rice.

Air-dried silt loam soil, passed through a 4-mm screen, was packed into 0.82-m-long and 0.50-m-diam metal drums, and given two wetting and drying cycles for proper settling. The soil had 264 kg available N ha⁻¹, 24.7 kg Olsen's P ha⁻¹, and 281 kg 1 N ammonium acetate-extractable K ha⁻¹. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of cultivar HPU741, two seedlings hill⁻¹ and five hills drum⁻¹, were transplanted. Each drum was fertilized with 100 kg N ha⁻¹ as urea, 17 kg P ha⁻¹ as superphosphate, and 33 kg K ha⁻¹ as potassium chloride. The soil in each drum was kept submerged with 30 mm water for the first 7 d. Thereafter, irrigation was regulated to achieve four water regimes in the root zone—30 mm continuous submergence of soil, and irrigation to the same water depth

Relationship between xylem water potential of rice and soil matric potential at 15 cm depth.

when matric potentials at 0.15 m soil depth reached -10, -20, and -30 kPa, as measured with mercury tensiometers.

The xylem water potential of rice plants was determined before each irrigation at 0700 h with a pressure chamber apparatus (Soil Moisture Equipment Corp., Santa Barbara, USA). A relationship was developed between soil matric potential and xylem water potential. Root and shoot growth, grain and straw yield, and yield parameters were determined. Root mass density (RMD) was determined at harvest by collecting soil cores, 0.15 m long and 0.10 m diam, 1 drum⁻¹, from the central plant in each drum.

The xylem water potential was positively correlated with soil matric

potential at 0.15 m depth (see figure). With every unit decrease in soil matric potential, the xylem water potential of rice plants decreased by 17.7 kPa. The xylem water potential of continuously watered plants was around -200 kPa.

Shoot growth rate, plant height, panicle weight, spikelet sterility, 1000-grain weight, and grain and straw yields of rice did not differ significantly at saturation and -10 kPa matric potential, but decreased at or below matric potentials of -20 kPa (see table). The RMD decreased progressively with the increase in water deficit. But lower RMD at -10 kPa compared with continuous soil submergence did not affect grain and straw yield of rice. The results indicate that ricefields do not

Effect of different soil water regimes on growth and yield of rice. Palampur, India.

Matric potential (kPa)	Shoot growth rate (mm d ⁻¹)		Plant height (cm)	RMD ^b (kg m ⁻³)	Panicle weight (g)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet sterility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grains (g hill ⁻¹)	Straw (g hill ⁻¹)	Total water use (mm)
	1-8 WAT ^a	8-12 WAT									
0	12.8	1.7	103.8	3.0	3.5	117	6	32.2	13.9	29.8	485
-10	12.6	1.7	103.0	2.8	3.6	114	6	32.5	13.5	29.1	418
-20	11.8	1.4	101.0	1.8	3.1	113	9	25.8	12.7	27.4	372
-30	11.6	1.2	99.0	1.6	3.1	109	11	25.7	12.6	27.2	322
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.3	5	1	1.8	0.6	0.9	22

^aWAT = weeks after transplanting. ^bRMD = root mass density.

need to be continuously flooded throughout the cropping period; a rice crop can be safely irrigated at -10 kPa matric suction without causing any

decline in rice yield. This suction, as observed in some field experiments, arrives in about 3-4 d in medium-textured soils in subtropical climates.

The procedure saved about 16% of the water used to keep soil continuously submerged under 30 mm of water. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Mass screening and identification of rice germplasm tolerant of light and temperature stress

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Rice adaptation to light and temperature stresses is the basis of stable yield. Few simple and easy techniques exist to test rice germplasm for tolerance for these stresses.

We screened rice germplasm for shading tolerance using the method of Murty (1992). We divided the identified varieties into two groups during elongation stage. One group was placed in natural light, the other in the shade (1/5 natural light). After 14 d, the dry weight of the two groups was measured at the booting stage. The ratio of dry weight under shading to that under natural light was used as the shading tolerance index.

At the same time, germplasm was screened for tolerance for photooxidation using the method of Jiao (1992). Mature rice leaves were detached at heading stage and submerged in a white tray filled with water containing 5 $\mu\text{mol CO}_2$ and 350 $\mu\text{mol O}_2$ under sunlight at 30-35 °C for 5-7 d. A transparent glass bar covered the leaves to prevent floating. Photooxidation-tolerant varieties whose chlorophyll contents were 3.0-4.78 mg dm^{-2} were graded 1-2, whereas sensitive varieties whose chlorophyll contents were 0.8-2.2 mg dm^{-2} were graded 4-5 (see table).

From 1993 to 1995, we identified 41 rice germplasm accessions using this technique. Results indicated four photosynthetic ecological types

Photooxidation and shading tolerance in different rice varieties.

Variety	Dry weight plant ⁻¹ (g)		S/N×100%	Photooxidative treatment	
	Natural light (N)	Shading (S)		Chl content (mg dm^{-2})	Grade ^a
1995					
Yue A (I)	5.37 ± 0.12	2.51 ± 0.12	46.72	1.45 ± 0.10	5
Yue A/R3049 (I)	5.15 ± 0.14	3.48 ± 0.17	67.57	1.66 ± 0.11	4
R3049 (I)	5.19 ± 0.15	1.78 ± 0.12	34.24	2.10 ± 0.21	4
Yue A/R3043 (I)	3.26 ± 0.15	2.68 ± 0.13	82.17	2.53 ± 0.17	3
R3043 (I)	4.33 ± 0.65	2.31 ± 0.15	53.31	3.36 ± 0.19	2
Yue A/R3034 (I)	4.38 ± 0.53	3.17 ± 0.21	72.44	1.77 ± 0.23	4
R3034 (I)	5.14 ± 0.21	2.16 ± 0.21	41.95	2.84 ± 0.29	3
Yue A/R3035 (I)	6.32 ± 0.25	3.33 ± 0.31	52.58	0.81 ± 0.09	5
R3035 (I)	4.90 ± 0.13	1.64 ± 0.11	33.54	1.22 ± 0.10	5
Yue A/R3044 (I)	5.75 ± 0.11	3.63 ± 0.29	62.91	2.49 ± 0.14	3
R3044 (I)	8.56 ± 0.25	3.29 ± 0.25	38.45	0.84 ± 0.08	5
Yue A/R437 (J)	6.35 ± 0.35	1.94 ± 0.15	30.59	1.45 ± 0.09	5
R437 (J)	6.06 ± 0.15	2.32 ± 0.19	38.32	2.24 ± 0.17	4
Yue A/J204 (J)	3.85 ± 0.20	2.46 ± 0.13	64.51	2.45 ± 0.10	3
J204 (J)	5.56 ± 0.12	1.61 ± 0.10	28.92	2.21 ± 0.13	4
Yue A/320500 (J)	6.88 ± 0.20	2.40 ± 0.12	34.94	1.99 ± 0.12	4
320500 (J)	5.58 ± 0.30	3.03 ± 0.31	54.30	1.28 ± 0.13	5
Yue A/30152 (I)	3.80 ± 0.17	1.94 ± 0.17	51.05	1.49 ± 0.10	5
Yue A/34077 (I)	4.65 ± 0.27	1.92 ± 0.15	41.29	2.58 ± 0.15	3
34077 (I)	4.42 ± 0.29	2.81 ± 0.21	63.50	3.14 ± 0.27	2
Yue A/42525 (I)	6.29 ± 0.21	2.75 ± 0.19	43.80	2.09 ± 0.19	4
1994					
Liuqianxin S/JW201 (J)	14.60 ± 1.68	6.90 ± 0.49	47.30	3.50 ± 0.25	3
Liuqianxin S (J)	15.50 ± 2.15	7.90 ± 0.58	51.00	3.31 ± 0.30	3
JW201 (J)	13.70 ± 1.89	8.80 ± 0.70	64.20	3.03 ± 0.25	3
JW207 (I)	12.10 ± 1.93	6.00 ± 0.57	49.60	2.21 ± 0.18	4
Liuqianxin S/JW207 (J)	13.90 ± 2.11	7.40 ± 0.49	53.20	2.33 ± 0.10	3
276 (J)	14.40 ± 2.99	6.50 ± 0.35	45.10	3.28 ± 0.27	4
Liuqianxin S/276 (J)	18.00 ± 2.29	10.50 ± 1.51	58.30	1.48 ± 0.09	5
Pelai 64S (I)	16.20 ± 2.44	6.20 ± 0.53	38.30	1.91 ± 0.11	4
1993					
02428 (J)	8.70 ± 0.53	5.90 ± 0.52	67.80	4.78 ± 0.35	1
Yayou 2 (J) B	10.50 ± 1.41	6.60 ± 0.39	62.90	3.93 ± 0.59	2
HX-3 (I)	28.01 ± 3.68	16.15 ± 3.10	57.66	2.56 ± 0.19	3
Minghui 63 (I)	16.05 ± 2.97	5.56 ± 0.29	34.61	2.27 ± 0.21	3
Shanyou 63 (I) D	11.50 ± 1.87	7.90 ± 0.48	68.70	1.73 ± 0.17	4
Jin gang 30 (I)	8.50 ± 0.36	4.30 ± 0.31	50.60	1.03 ± 0.16	5
Xiangxian (I) F	11.40 ± 2.16	3.10 ± 0.30	27.20	1.20 ± 0.11	5
Tsukushibare (J) C	7.00 ± 0.36	2.10 ± 0.21	30.30	3.03 ± 0.31	2
Corn-rice (I)	4.60 ± 0.38	3.30 ± 0.21	71.70	1.36 ± 0.10	5
Nanjing 14 (I) E	8.70 ± 0.47	2.90 ± 0.19	33.30	2.75 ± 0.17	3
Wuyugeng (J) A	7.00 ± 0.41	4.10 ± 0.35	58.60	3.78 ± 0.43	2
Peiai 64S/JW201 (J)	16.10 ± 2.74	6.20 ± 0.58	38.50	1.40 ± 0.10	5

^aGrades (scores): 1 = green; 2 = tip is yellowish; 3 = 1/3 is yellowish; 4 = 1/2 is yellowish; 5 = whole leaf is yellowish. Shading period was from elongation to booting. Photooxidative treatment was conducted at booting stage for 6 d.

adapted to light intensity. One was adapted to a wide range of light intensities, including japonica rice 02428, Wuyugeng, and indica-japonica

hybrid rice YueA/ R 3043, Yayou 2. During the heading stage, photosynthetic rate at high (40 °C) and low temperatures (15 °C) was determined